

Chongqing Adolescent Twin Study (CATS) Data Use Agreement

1. Introduction

This Data Use Agreement (“DUA”) sets forth the terms and conditions governing the use of the Chongqing Adolescent Twin Study (“CATS”) dataset. Researchers and their institutions (“Recipients”) who access and utilize this dataset must uphold the privacy, confidentiality, and rights of the study participants. By signing this DUA, you and your institution agree to:

- (1) Adhere to all terms and conditions described herein.
- (2) Ensure that all individuals (collectively, “Recipients”) listed in this DUA follow these terms when handling CATS data.
- (3) Accept responsibility for any misuse or breach of these terms by the Recipients named in this DUA.

2. The CATS Dataset

The CATS dataset consists of research data involving human subjects and is accessible through the Brain Science Data Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (<https://doi.org/10.12412/BSDC.1736128526.40001>). All direct identifiers have been removed to protect participant confidentiality and privacy. By receiving access to this dataset, Recipients agree to comply with this DUA and all applicable privacy, confidentiality, and ethical standards.

3. Access Request

Recipients seeking access to the CATS dataset must complete the following steps:

- (1) Register for an account with the Brain Science Data Center.
- (2) Submit this DUA, duly signed by the Lead Recipient and certified by an authorized Institutional Official, via email to: zhiwei.ma@shanghaitech.edu.cn.
- (3) Complete the data access request process on the Brain Science Data Center website.

Access to the CATS dataset will be granted upon completion of the above procedures.

4. Data Usage Terms and Conditions

4.1 Non-Transferability of Agreement

This DUA is non-transferable. If a Recipient changes institutional affiliation, that Recipient will be removed from this DUA and must reapply under their new institution to regain access. If the Lead Recipient leaves the institution, they may designate another Recipient named in this DUA to assume their role, subject to the same terms and conditions.

4.2 No Distribution of Data

Recipients shall not share, distribute, sell, or transfer the dataset—or any part thereof—to any third party, external system, or organization. Any questions regarding data sharing must be directed to the Recipient’s Institutional Review Board (“IRB”) or Human Research Ethics Committee (“HREC”), as applicable.

4.3 No Re-identification of Subjects

Recipients shall not attempt to re-identify any individual participants or contact them. If any identifying information is inadvertently discovered, Recipients must immediately notify Zhiwei Ma

(zhiwei.ma@shanghaitech.edu.cn). Any publication or dissemination of information that could lead to re-identification of participants is strictly prohibited. All inquiries regarding participant privacy should be addressed to the Recipient’s IRB or HREC.

4.4 Compliance with Applicable Human Subjects Protection and Institutional Requirements

Recipients shall comply with all applicable laws, regulations, and institutional policies governing the protection of human subjects. It is each Recipient’s responsibility to determine whether IRB or HREC review is required. Recipients must consider potential risks to individuals, groups, or society and implement measures to minimize harm. Any unanticipated risks or adverse events related to the use of CATS data must be promptly reported to the appropriate ethics body.

4.5 Security

Recipients must maintain appropriate technical, administrative, and physical safeguards to protect the dataset from unauthorized access, breaches, or misuse. This includes ensuring secure data storage—whether local or cloud-based—and restricting access to authorized personnel only. By signing this DUA, Recipients affirm that they have a security plan in place to meet these standards.

4.6 Deletion of Data

Upon completion of the research project, Recipients must permanently delete all copies of the dataset from local and/or cloud storage. If retention is required (e.g., to satisfy legal or regulatory obligations), the data must remain securely stored with access strictly limited to individuals covered by this DUA and relevant ethics approvals.

4.7 Acknowledgements

Recipients agree to acknowledge the CATS dataset and its corresponding Digital Object Identifier (“DOI”) in any presentations, publications, or disclosures derived from its use. Proper attribution must be included wherever the data is referenced.

5. CATS Data Recipient Information and Certification

5.1 Lead Recipient

First Name: _____ Last Name: _____ Degree: _____

Institution: _____

City: _____ State/Province: _____ Country : _____

Phone: _____ Email: _____

Brain Science Data Center Username: _____

5.2 Other Recipients

(Please list additional Recipients below, if applicable. Attach extra pages as needed.)

First Name: _____ Last Name: _____ Degree: _____

Institution: _____

City: _____ State/Province: _____ Country : _____

Phone: _____ Email: _____

5.3 Authorized Institutional Official

Name: _____ Position: _____ Email Address: _____

5.4 Signatures

By signing and dating this DUA, the Lead Recipient and the Authorized Institutional Official confirm that:

- (1) They have read and agree to comply with all terms and conditions set forth in this DUA.
- (2) All individuals listed as Recipients have been informed of, understand, and agree to abide by these obligations.
- (3) The institution has reviewed and approved the terms of this DUA and will oversee compliance accordingly.

Lead Recipient Signature _____ Date _____

Authorized Institutional Official Signature _____ Date _____

Please submit completed and signed DUAs to: Zhiwei Ma (zhiwei.ma@shanghaitech.edu.cn)